

SURGICAL MANAGEMENT OF TRAUMATIC SPINAL INJURIES AT TANGANYIKA HOSPITAL

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ABSTRACT

Traumatic spinal injuries are a significant public health concern requiring urgent diagnostic and therapeutic intervention. Globally, their incidence ranges from 40 to 50 cases per million annually, with limited data available in Burundi. Common causes include road traffic accidents, falls, and workplace injuries, often affecting fragile transitional spinal regions. Surgery is indicated for cases involving spinal compression, deformity, or instability. Historically, Burundian patients had to seek treatment abroad due to a lack of local expertise and resources. However, since January 2024, Tanganyika Hospital has commenced spinal surgeries under the expertise of Dr. Oscar Niyonzima, marking a milestone in the local management of spinal trauma.

Objective: *To describe the epidemiological, clinical, therapeutic and evolutionary aspects of spinal trauma patients operated at Tanganyika Hospital.*

Keywords: Spinal Trauma, Surgical Management, Tanganyika Hospital, Burundi Healthcare, Neurosurgery

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INTRODUCTION

Spinal trauma is a public health problem. It is a diagnostic and therapeutic emergency. There is an incidence of 40 to 50 new cases per million worldwide, a frequency of 2,500 cases per year in France and an incidence of 1,800 new cases per million in the United States. In Burundi, detailed data on the national territory is rare. The most frequently observed accident mechanisms are road traffic accidents, falls from height and accidents at work.

The entire spinal column is made up of three segments: the cervical spine, the dorsal spine and the lumbosacral spine. The areas where these segments meet, known as "hinges", are fragile and prone to traumatic injury (3; 4). Treatment begins in the pre-hospital phase with spinal immobilisation. Medical transport is also compulsory to avoid aggravating the injuries. In the case of spinal trauma, the indications for surgery are spinal compression, deformity and instability (1; 4). In Burundi, patients suffering from spinal injuries for which surgery is indicated have always had to travel abroad for better care, due to the lack of technical facilities and staff specialising in this field.

Since the return of Dr Oscar Niyonzima, a neurosurgeon at Tanganyika Hospital, one of the country's private 3rd category facility, this situation is changing. Burundi has acquired good-quality spinal surgery equipment and, since January 2024, such surgery can be performed locally.

Fig. 1: Equipment available for spinal surgery at Tanganyika Hospital.

PATIENTS AND METHODS

Our study was prospective and took place over a six-month period, from 10 January to 9 July 2024. The study population consisted of patients operated on for spinal trauma. Patients undergoing spinal surgery for degenerative, tumour, infectious or malformative pathologies were excluded. Patients were assessed on arrival at hospital, during hospitalisation and at three months post-operatively. The variables studied were: age, sex, profession, level of education, clinico-radiological data, management and outcome. Data entry and analysis were performed using Excel and SPSS software. Institutional ethical approval was obtained from the management of Tanganyika Hospital.

RESULTS

Thirty-one patients were included in our study, fourteen for cervical spine trauma and seventeen for dorsolumbar spine trauma. From an epidemiological point of view, the average age of the patients was 35 ± 6 years, with extremes of 21 and 77 years. The age group most affected was between 30 and 40. The male/female ratio was 4:1. By occupation, security guards were the most numerous (27.8%), followed by civil servants (23.1%), drivers (19.8%) and farmers (11.1%). According to patients' level of education, 29% had primary education, 21% secondary education and 9% university education.

According to the mechanism of trauma, public road accidents were the most common (42%), followed by falls (21.51%) and work-related accidents (19.1%).

Clinical manifestations were frequently represented by tetraplegia, predominantly crural (64.48%) for cervical lesions, associated with genital-sphincter disorders (88.12%), a spinal syndrome (100%) and vegetative disorders, such as dyspnoea (0.93%).

For dorsolumbar lesions, complete paraplegia was noted in 59.82% of cases, associated with a spinal syndrome (100%) and sphincter disorders (67.93%). All our patients underwent a CT scan of the spine in order to clearly visualise the traumatic lesions.

Table1: Traumatic lesions observed according to CT scan results

Traumatic injuries	n	%
C4-C5 dislocation fracture	6	19,35
C5-C6 dislocation	2	6,45
C5-C6 dislocation fracture	2	6,45
C6-C7 dislocation fracture	4	12,90
D12 fracture with posterior wall recession	11	35,48
D11 fracture with medullary compression	5	16,12
L12 fracture with rotation of its body	1	3,22

Fig 2: CT scan of the lumbar spine with a comminuted fracture of L2 causing spinal cord compression, pre- and post-operative image.

Fig 3: CT scan of cervical spine with C5-C6 cervical fracture/dislocation, pre-and post-operative image.

All our patients underwent therapeutic surgery. The average time between the trauma and the operation was 4 ± 2 days, with extremes ranging from 1 to 15 days. Cervical spine injuries were diagnosed as osteo-disco-ligamentous instability associated with spinal cord compression. Reduction with anterolateral cervical arthrodesis was then performed. For injuries to the dorsolumbar spine, osteosynthesis was performed at two levels above and below the spine, combined with decompressive laminectomy via a posterior approach. In all cases, the aim of the operation was to decompress the spinal cord while stabilising the injured level. All our patients received antibiotic prophylaxis, analgesics and corticosteroids for the first 48 hours to prevent spinal cord and/or radicular oedema. They also all received physical treatment to re-educate their motor skills. The average postoperative hospital stay was 16 ± 3 days, with extremes ranging from 7 to 90 days. The evolution was marked by a progressive recovery of neurological signs (motor deficit and sphincter disorders) in 58.06% of cases, and by the persistence of sequelae of motor deficit in 32.25% of cases. There were also three cases of death.

Table 2: Three months postoperative outcome

Monitoring parameters	%
Progressive recovery of neurological signs	58,06
Persistence of motor deficit	32,25
Decubitus complications (bedsores, infections, thrombosis)	19,35
Death	9,67

DISCUSSION

The incidence of 31 patients over a six-month period shows that this is a frequent pathology. It often affects young subjects. In our study, the mean age was 35 and the male/female ratio was 4:1, which is consistent with the literature. Our study is comparable to that of Najib Derhem, who found an average age of 37, with a ratio of 3 men to 1 woman. Accidents on public roads, falls and accidents at work were the main causes of trauma in our study. This phenomenon is thought to be linked to the failure of some drivers to comply with the highway code and the failure of people engaged in high-risk activities to wear protective equipment. These results are also consistent with the literature (1). Clinical manifestations depend on the intensity of the accident and the level of injury. Traumatic injuries were more frequent in the hinge areas of the spine. These results are similar to those of N. Derhem (8). This is also consistent with the literature. In the cervical region, the most frequent injury was a dislocation-fracture, while in the dorsolumbar region, it was a compression-fracture of the hinge bones. Trauma to the cervical spine can be treated by a double surgical approach (posterior approach and anterolateral approach) depending on the indications. All our patients were operated on using the right anterolateral approach, and then underwent arthrodesis using a bone graft and a screw plate under fluoroscopic control, the technique most commonly used for most traumatic injuries of the cervical spine (3). For injuries to the dorsolumbar spine, a posteromedial approach was used. Surgery consisted of fixation (stabilisation) and decompression of the injured area. Scopically-guided pedicle targeting was performed at both levels above and below the lesion. After the pedicle sights, rods adjusted to the anatomical curvatures of the spine were inserted, followed by a decompressive laminectomy. This technique is also commonly used in surgery for thoracolumbar injuries (4). The average time between the accident and the operation was long (4 ± 2 days). This may be explained partly by transport difficulties and partly by a lack of information. Some people were unaware that this type of surgery was currently available in Burundi. Lack of financial resources or health insurance is also thought to be one of the causes of delays in treatment. Ideally, in cases of neurological deficit linked to spinal cord compression, surgery should be performed within 4 to 8 hours of the trauma (1;3;5).

CONCLUSION

Vertebro medullary trauma is a frequent pathology. It is a medical and surgical emergency. The most frequent causes are road accidents, falls and accidents at work. The main indications for surgery are neurological deficits, deformities and spinal instability. The aim of surgery is to ensure spinal stability and decompression of nerve structures. This surgery is currently feasible in Burundi. However, we are seeking to move towards minimally invasive spinal surgery.

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